

Explaining Renewable Electricity Expansion in Europe: Structural Conditions, Diffusion, and Leadership

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Abstract

European countries differ markedly in the expansion of wind and solar electricity. A dynamic agent-based model is developed for 34 countries over 2015–2024, treating national electricity systems as heterogeneous and interconnected agents. Renewable adoption is decomposed into domestic proactivity, international reactivity, and persistent country-specific leadership. The model accounts for economic conditions, electricity-system structure, resource potential, geography, policy support, technological maturity, and exposure to renewable expansion in connected countries. The results show that leadership differs from simple observed growth and is strongly technology specific. Lithuania, Finland, and Moldova emerge as leading wind performers, while Hungary, Moldova, and Estonia lead in solar. Several countries with favourable structural conditions expand more slowly than predicted. The framework provides a conditional measure of renewable-energy leadership and clarifies how domestic fundamentals and international diffusion jointly shape national transition paths.

Keywords: renewable electricity; agent-based modelling; energy transition; policy diffusion; wind energy; solar energy; renewable leadership

1. Introduction

The expansion of renewable electricity has become a central component of European climate, industrial, and energy-security policy. European countries have adopted increasingly ambitious decarbonisation targets, while technological progress and declining costs have made wind and solar power economically viable across a growing range of locations. Nevertheless, renewable-electricity deployment remains highly uneven. Some countries have rapidly increased the contribution of wind or solar power to electricity generation, whereas others with apparently

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similar income levels, natural resources, and policy commitments have progressed much more slowly. Previous research attributes these differences to combinations of economic development, electricity-system structure, policy support, institutional conditions, natural-resource availability, and spatial factors (Marques et al., 2010; Aguirre & Ibikunle, 2014; Yu et al., 2021; García-Riazuelo et al., 2025). Explaining this variation is important not only for evaluating national energy-transition strategies but also for understanding how technological change spreads across interconnected economies.

Conventional comparisons of renewable-energy performance generally rank countries according to installed capacity, renewable-generation shares, or observed growth rates. These measures provide useful descriptive information, but they do not necessarily identify genuine leadership. The environmental-governance literature distinguishes between countries that achieve ambitious domestic outcomes, countries that pioneer new policies, and countries that actively influence the behaviour of followers (Jänicke, 2005; Liefferink & Wurzel, 2017; Wurzel et al., 2019). Countries with abundant wind or solar resources, high income, favourable geography, elevated electricity prices, or supportive policy frameworks would be expected to expand renewable generation more rapidly even in the absence of exceptional institutional or political performance. Similarly, countries beginning from a very low renewable share may record large percentage increases without developing a particularly strong or persistent transition strategy. Absolute deployment and observed growth therefore combine structural opportunity, technological maturity, international exposure, and country-specific performance.

This article develops a conditional interpretation of renewable-energy leadership. Leadership is defined as persistent expansion beyond the level predicted by a country's observable structural conditions and its exposure to developments in other countries. A country is therefore considered a leader not simply because it has installed a large amount of renewable capacity or achieved a high renewable share, but because it systematically performs better than would be expected given its economic resources, initial electricity mix, natural potential, geographical conditions, policy environment, and position within the European economic and geographical network. Conversely, a country may possess favourable structural conditions while expanding renewable electricity more slowly than predicted. Such a country is classified as an underperformer despite having a relatively high observed level of renewable generation. This approach builds on the distinction between pioneering behaviour, leadership, and realised environmental performance, while providing an operational country-level measure based on conditional outcomes rather than political declarations or absolute deployment (Jänicke, 2005; Liefferink & Wurzel, 2017).

The analytical framework distinguishes three mechanisms behind renewable-electricity expansion: domestic proactivity, international reactivity, and residual leadership. Domestic proactivity represents the adoption pressure generated by national characteristics. These include existing dependence on fossil fuels, the initial composition of electricity generation, renewable-resource potential, geographical suitability, income per capita, electricity prices, and public policy support. Empirical studies show that these factors influence renewable deployment through investment capacity, technological lock-in, resource availability, relative generation costs, and the incentives created by public policy (Johnstone et al., 2010; Marques

& Fuinhas, 2011; Polzin et al., 2015; Cadoret & Padovano, 2016; Bersalli et al., 2020). Together, they describe the expansion that would normally be expected from a country's internal economic, technological, geographical, and institutional conditions.

International reactivity captures the possibility that renewable deployment in one country responds to recent expansion elsewhere. European electricity transitions do not occur in isolated national systems. Countries observe foreign policy experiments, share equipment markets and supply chains, trade with one another, participate in common regulatory institutions, and learn from the technological and administrative experience of connected economies. International technological knowledge and domestic absorptive capacity jointly influence renewable adoption, while geographical proximity, trade relationships, policy emulation, and common institutional environments can facilitate cross-border diffusion (Popp et al., 2011; Verdolini & Galeotti, 2011; Fadly & Fontes, 2019; Baldwin et al., 2019). Renewable expansion abroad can reduce uncertainty, demonstrate commercial viability, generate technological learning, encourage policy imitation, and contribute to the development of cross-border supply chains. These effects are unlikely to be distributed uniformly. Developments in geographically close, economically large, commercially connected, or institutionally similar countries may exert greater influence than developments in distant or weakly connected economies.

The third mechanism, residual leadership, captures persistent country-specific performance that remains unexplained after domestic conditions and international exposure have been taken into account. Comparative research shows that renewable deployment depends not only on formal policies or resource endowments but also on political coalitions, institutional arrangements, administrative capacity, inherited energy structures, and the ability to implement policy instruments effectively (Jacobsson & Lauber, 2006; Četković & Buzogány, 2020). The residual component may therefore reflect administrative effectiveness, political commitment, permitting capacity, social acceptance, access to finance, industrial specialisation, implementation quality, or other relatively stable characteristics that cannot be measured directly. Leadership is interpreted cautiously as conditional and residual performance rather than as a direct measure of any single institutional attribute.

The distinction between these mechanisms is particularly relevant because solar and wind technologies may follow different diffusion processes. Solar photovoltaic systems are comparatively standardised, modular, internationally traded, and deployable at multiple scales. Their expansion may therefore respond relatively quickly to foreign technological progress, falling equipment costs, and policy demonstration effects. Wind power is generally more dependent on local resource conditions, grid infrastructure, planning procedures, project scale, construction capacity, and public acceptance. Patent-based research also indicates that renewable technologies generate different patterns of knowledge spillovers, with solar technologies exhibiting broader technological connections than wind technologies (Noailly & Shestalova, 2017). Comparative evidence from European countries similarly shows that solar and wind expansion is shaped by different political coalitions, market structures, and technology-specific barriers (Četković & Buzogány, 2020). The domestic and international

determinants of adoption, as well as the identity of leaders and followers, may consequently differ substantially between the two technologies.

To examine these processes, the article develops a dynamic agent-based model of wind- and solar-electricity adoption across 34 European countries between 2015 and 2024. Each country is represented as a heterogeneous and interconnected agent. Countries update their renewable-electricity shares according to a bounded transition rule combining domestic characteristics, lagged renewable expansion among relevant foreign countries, a persistent country-specific effect, and temporary annual shocks. International exposure is represented through a gravity-based network incorporating geographical distance, bilateral trade, shared borders, linguistic proximity, and the economic size of potentially influential countries. The model is estimated separately for wind and solar, allowing the determinants of proactivity, the strength of cross-country reactivity, and the distribution of leadership to vary by technology.

Agent-based models are particularly suitable for analysing energy transitions because they can represent heterogeneous actors, recursive decision rules, social and economic interactions, path dependence, feedback mechanisms, and nonlinear technological diffusion (Robinson & Rai, 2015; Palmer et al., 2015; Hoekstra et al., 2017; Lamperti et al., 2020). Most existing applications, however, model households, firms, investors, power plants, or technologies as agents. Some recent work has incorporated interactions between neighbouring electricity markets, showing that national policy decisions can redirect renewable investment across borders (Melliger & Chappin, 2022). The present model extends this literature by treating countries themselves as heterogeneous agents embedded in an international network.

The model also incorporates the cumulative and bounded nature of technological adoption. Renewable deployment is path dependent because previous investment creates infrastructure, specialised knowledge, supply chains, administrative experience, industrial capabilities, and political constituencies that facilitate subsequent expansion. Empirical and historical studies of renewable transitions emphasise the importance of technological persistence, policy continuity, market formation, and accumulated capabilities (Jacobsson & Lauber, 2006; Marques & Fuinhas, 2011). At the same time, technological growth cannot continue indefinitely at a constant rate because countries face geographical, technical, infrastructural, market, and institutional constraints. The resulting transition mechanism produces an S-shaped adoption path in which growth is initially limited, accelerates after sufficient technological capacity has developed, and gradually slows as the technology approaches its feasible ceiling.

The analysis addresses four principal research questions. First, which domestic economic, geographical, energy-system, and policy characteristics explain the expansion of solar and wind electricity? Second, to what extent do countries react to recent renewable deployment in geographically and economically connected foreign economies? Third, which countries exhibit persistent leadership or underperformance after structural conditions and international exposure have been controlled for? Fourth, do the determinants of proactivity, the strength of international reactivity, and the resulting leadership rankings differ between solar and wind?

The article contributes to the renewable-energy literature in three respects. First, it replaces descriptive rankings with a structural benchmark that distinguishes observed deployment from

performance relative to national potential. This permits the identification of countries that outperform despite relatively unfavourable conditions, as well as countries that underuse strong structural advantages. Second, it explicitly separates domestically generated adoption pressure from behavioural reactions to renewable expansion abroad. The gravity-based network allows foreign influence to depend on economic and geographical connectivity rather than assuming that all countries respond equally to one another. Third, it extends agent-based energy-transition modelling by treating countries, rather than firms, households, or individual technologies, as heterogeneous agents embedded in an international influence network. This approach connects country-level empirical estimation with a dynamic framework capable of reproducing adoption paths and evaluating counterfactual scenarios.

The results demonstrate that renewable-energy leadership differs from simple observed growth. After controlling for structural conditions and international exposure, Lithuania, Finland, and Moldova emerge among the strongest conditional performers in wind expansion, while Hungary, Moldova, and Estonia exhibit particularly strong solar performance. At the same time, several countries possessing favourable economic or natural conditions expand renewable generation more slowly than predicted. The findings also suggest that geopolitical and energy-security conditions are associated with renewable deployment: countries located closer to Russia or historically more dependent on Russian energy tend to exhibit faster renewable-electricity expansion after other observable factors are considered. This pattern is consistent with an energy-security incentive to accelerate substitution away from imported fossil fuels, although it should not be interpreted as establishing a strictly causal effect.

More broadly, the findings show that structural potential does not mechanically determine renewable performance. Natural resources, income, electricity-system composition, and policy support shape the opportunity to expand renewable generation, but countries differ in their capacity to convert those opportunities into actual deployment. International connections also contribute to the transmission of renewable technologies, policy experience, and investment incentives. The relative importance of these mechanisms differs between wind and solar, confirming the need to analyse the two technologies separately.

The remainder of the article is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature on renewable-energy adoption, international policy and technological diffusion, energy leadership, and agent-based modelling. Section 3 describes the country-level, technology-specific, policy, and bilateral data. Section 4 presents the agent-based model, the decomposition of adoption pressure, the gravity-based influence network, and the estimation procedure. Section 5 reports the domestic determinants, cross-country reactivity estimates, model fit, and technology-specific leadership rankings. Section 6 discusses the theoretical and policy implications, together with the limitations of the analysis. Section 7 concludes.

2. Literature Review and Conceptual Framework

Renewable-electricity expansion is shaped by a combination of domestic structural conditions, policy interventions, technological accumulation, and interactions between countries. Existing studies have generally examined these mechanisms separately. One literature estimates the economic, geographical, political, and energy-system determinants of renewable deployment.

A second investigates the international diffusion of policies, technologies, and knowledge. A third discusses environmental leadership and the distinction between pioneers, leaders, and followers. A fourth uses agent-based models to represent heterogeneous actors and nonlinear technological transitions. The framework developed in this article integrates these strands by distinguishing domestic proactivity, international reactivity, and persistent conditional leadership.

The empirical literature identifies economic development as one of the most frequently examined determinants of renewable-energy deployment. Higher GDP per capita can facilitate renewable investment by increasing access to finance, strengthening administrative capacity, supporting electricity-grid modernisation, and allowing governments or consumers to absorb the initial costs of emerging technologies. Wealthier countries may also face stronger public demand for environmental protection and possess more developed innovation systems. Nevertheless, the relationship is not necessarily linear. High income does not guarantee rapid renewable deployment, particularly when electricity systems are already dominated by incumbent technologies or when existing low-carbon generation reduces the pressure to introduce additional renewables.

Early European panel studies show that economic capacity must be considered alongside energy-system structure and political conditions. Marques et al. (2010) find that conventional-energy interests and dependence on established fossil technologies can restrain renewable deployment. Marques and Fuinhas (2011) subsequently demonstrate that renewable development is strongly dynamic: current adoption depends partly on previous deployment, indicating persistence and path dependence. Global evidence similarly shows that economic development, energy demand, institutional quality, and public policies have heterogeneous effects across countries rather than producing a single universal transition trajectory (Aguirre & Ibikunle, 2014).

Electricity prices constitute a second economic mechanism. Higher wholesale or final-user prices can improve the relative competitiveness of wind and solar electricity, reduce the payback period of renewable investments, and increase incentives for self-generation. However, the interpretation of electricity prices is complicated by endogeneity. Prices may increase because of fossil-fuel costs, taxation, network investment, market design, or the costs of integrating renewables already installed. A positive association between prices and renewable expansion therefore does not necessarily imply that price increases independently cause adoption. Prices are better understood as part of the economic environment in which investment decisions are made.

Fossil-fuel dependence is also theoretically ambiguous. A high initial fossil share creates substantial scope for substitution and may strengthen energy-security and decarbonisation incentives. At the same time, fossil-intensive systems contain physical assets, specialised labour, regulatory structures, political constituencies, and financial interests that can delay technological change. Marques et al. (2010) interpret the restraining influence of conventional-energy interests as evidence that incumbent structures matter. This interpretation is consistent with the broader concept of carbon lock-in, under which historical investment decisions make

later transitions costly even when alternative technologies become technically viable. The effect of fossil dependence may consequently change over time: it can initially impede renewable expansion but later generate stronger replacement pressure once political or economic conditions change.

The initial presence of other electricity sources is equally important. Countries with extensive hydropower or nuclear generation may already possess relatively low-carbon electricity systems and therefore face less immediate pressure to expand wind or solar power. These technologies can also occupy a large share of electricity demand, reducing the market space available to new generation. Conversely, flexible hydropower can facilitate the integration of variable wind and solar electricity by providing balancing capacity. The relationship between the initial non-fossil electricity mix and subsequent renewable expansion is therefore technology and system specific.

Natural-resource potential and geography impose more direct constraints. Solar irradiation affects the productivity of photovoltaic capacity, while wind speed and wind-power density influence the economic viability of onshore and offshore projects. Coastlines, terrain, land availability, latitude, population density, and settlement patterns alter installation costs and the availability of suitable sites. Resource endowments nevertheless explain only part of the observed variation. Countries with similar physical potential frequently follow very different deployment paths, while countries with moderate solar irradiation have sometimes achieved higher photovoltaic shares than sunnier economies. Natural conditions define technological opportunities, but institutions, infrastructure, policies, financing, and implementation determine whether those opportunities are used.

Recent research increasingly treats renewable deployment as spatially heterogeneous. Yu et al. (2021) show that renewable penetration in European electricity systems displays both temporal and spatial variation and cannot be explained by a purely static national model. García-Riazuelo et al. (2025) extend this perspective to European regions, examining how socioeconomic and geographical drivers are associated with the spatial distribution of renewable energy. This literature supports the inclusion of geographical characteristics while also indicating that spatial patterns may reflect interactions between neighbouring or connected territories rather than resource conditions alone.

Public policy is another central determinant. Governments influence renewable investment through feed-in tariffs, premiums, auctions, renewable portfolio requirements, investment subsidies, tax incentives, carbon prices, grid-access rules, permitting procedures, and long-term targets. Carley (2009) shows that the existence of a renewable-electricity policy is not by itself sufficient to ensure substantial deployment. Policy design, bindingness, duration, and implementation conditions determine whether formal commitments translate into investment. Marques and Fuinhas (2012) similarly find that the effects of European renewable policies depend on the instruments and institutional environments considered.

Different instruments may also affect different stages of the innovation and adoption process. Johnstone et al. (2010), using patent data, find that renewable-energy policies stimulate technological innovation, but the effectiveness of particular instruments varies by technology.

Broad market-based mechanisms may be sufficient for relatively mature technologies, whereas more targeted support can be necessary for technologies that remain comparatively expensive. This result implies that a single aggregate policy indicator may conceal important differences in policy composition and technological maturity.

The credibility and stability of policy support are particularly important for capital-intensive investments. Polzin et al. (2015) find that public policy affects institutional investment in renewable generating capacity by changing project risk and expected returns. Regulatory measures and long-term strategic commitments can complement direct financial support by reducing uncertainty. Bersalli et al. (2020), comparing Europe and Latin America, likewise conclude that renewable-policy effectiveness depends on the combination of instruments rather than on isolated incentives. Policy packages are therefore likely to matter more than the simple number of measures formally in place.

Political and institutional factors determine whether policies are adopted, maintained, and implemented. Cadoret and Padovano (2016) show that political variables possess explanatory power alongside economic, energy, and environmental conditions in European renewable policy. Government ideology, political competition, institutional constraints, lobbying, and the distribution of transition costs can affect policy ambition. Aguirre and Ibikunle (2014) also emphasise governance and policy quality in explaining cross-country renewable growth. Institutional capacity matters because renewable deployment requires more than target setting: authorities must organise auctions, process permits, coordinate grid access, enforce contracts, and respond to local opposition.

The determinants literature therefore produces three general conclusions. First, renewable expansion is multidimensional: no single variable such as income, resource availability, or policy support is sufficient. Second, adoption is path dependent because previous deployment creates infrastructure, experience, firms, supply chains, and administrative knowledge. Third, the effects are technology specific. Solar and wind differ in modularity, project scale, construction time, resource dependence, grid requirements, and exposure to local planning constraints. These conclusions motivate the proactivity component of the present model, which combines initial electricity structure, economic capacity, prices, policy support, geography, and technology-specific resource potential.

National renewable transitions do not take place independently. Technologies, equipment, engineering knowledge, policy models, investment practices, and expectations cross national borders. International diffusion can reduce the costs and uncertainty of adoption even when a country does not generate the relevant innovation domestically. The literature distinguishes several related mechanisms: technological knowledge spillovers, equipment trade, demonstration effects, policy learning, regulatory imitation, supply-chain integration, and direct responses to developments in geographically or economically connected countries.

Popp et al. (2011) examine the international diffusion of renewable technologies and show that access to technological knowledge facilitates adoption, although domestic absorptive capacity remains important. A country must possess sufficient technical, institutional, and human capabilities to use knowledge developed elsewhere. Technology diffusion is therefore not

automatic: foreign innovation creates opportunities, but national capabilities determine whether these opportunities result in deployment. The same logic applies to policy diffusion. Governments may observe foreign measures, but their ability to reproduce the resulting outcomes depends on domestic administrative, financial, and infrastructural conditions.

Verdolini and Galeotti (2011) distinguish domestic knowledge accumulation from international spillovers in energy innovation. Their results indicate that both domestic experience and foreign knowledge contribute to technological development. International spillovers are particularly relevant for countries that are not located at the technological frontier, but they do not eliminate the importance of internal innovative capacity. Pfeiffer and Mulder (2013) reach a related conclusion for developing countries: income, energy demand, previous technological experience, policy conditions, and domestic capabilities influence both the initial adoption and subsequent diffusion of renewable technologies.

Patent citations provide a more direct measure of knowledge transmission. Noailly and Shestalova (2017) show that renewable technologies generate different patterns of intra-technology, inter-technology, and external knowledge spillovers. Wind knowledge is comparatively concentrated within its own technological field, whereas solar and storage technologies generate broader connections with other technological domains. Such differences imply that the international diffusion of wind and solar may occur through different channels and at different speeds.

Environmental policy can strengthen international technology diffusion by creating markets for cleaner technologies and increasing incentives to acquire foreign knowledge. Verdolini and Bosetti (2017) show that stronger environmental policies promote the international diffusion of cleaner electricity-generation technologies. International climate commitments can have similar effects. Miyamoto and Takeuchi (2019) find that the Kyoto Protocol increased international patent applications for renewable technologies among countries with emissions targets, with particularly visible effects for solar technology and for countries subject to more stringent commitments. These findings indicate that domestic and international policy cannot be treated as entirely separate: policy commitments alter both national demand and the cross-border circulation of technology.

Geographical proximity provides another diffusion channel. Nearby countries are more likely to share infrastructure, electricity markets, environmental conditions, suppliers, professional networks, and political reference groups. Fadly and Fontes (2019) find evidence that renewable adoption is associated with deployment in geographically proximate countries. Their results suggest that national expansion may be facilitated by demonstration effects, information exchange, regional capital formation, and the development of shared supply chains. Spatial correlation, however, does not necessarily imply behavioural imitation. Neighbouring countries may adopt similar technologies because they possess similar resources or are exposed to common regulatory and economic shocks. Empirical models must therefore distinguish foreign influence from correlated domestic conditions.

Trade relationships can transmit renewable technology even when countries are not geographically adjacent. Imports provide access to equipment and components, while exports

and participation in international value chains create domestic industrial interests that may support deployment. Bilateral trade also increases the circulation of information and links firms, investors, and public institutions. Economic size affects this relationship because developments in large markets can influence equipment prices, technological standards, policy expectations, and supply-chain investment beyond their borders. The direction of influence may therefore be asymmetric: a major economy can affect a smaller trading partner more strongly than the smaller country affects the major economy.

Policy diffusion constitutes a related but distinct process. Governments may emulate policies adopted by countries viewed as successful, politically similar, economically comparable, or institutionally influential. Baldwin et al. (2019) use directed country-pair relationships to examine renewable-policy emulation globally. They find that the identity of the reference country depends on political relationships, similarities between electricity systems, and other forms of international connection. Countries do not imitate all foreign policies equally; they select models from relevant peers.

Demonstration effects can operate even without formal policy transfer. Successful deployment abroad provides information about construction costs, grid integration, public acceptance, and the commercial performance of a technology. This evidence reduces uncertainty for investors and policymakers. Technological learning can also lower costs internationally as cumulative production increases. However, international spillovers rarely substitute completely for domestic support. Research on wind diffusion indicates that learning spillovers can reinforce national adoption, but countries without effective domestic demand-pull mechanisms may still fail to develop substantial wind capacity.

The diffusion literature therefore supports a network-based rather than purely geographical representation of international influence. Distance and shared borders capture spatial proximity, but bilateral trade, linguistic similarity, and partner-country economic size capture additional channels of information, equipment flows, policy learning, and visibility. The present model combines these dimensions in a gravity-based network. The network does not assume that countries mechanically copy foreign behaviour. Instead, it measures the external adoption environment to which each country is exposed.

The use of lagged foreign expansion is also consistent with the diffusion literature. Policy learning, investment responses, equipment-market adjustment, and demonstration effects require time. A country observes deployment elsewhere and only subsequently changes its own policies, expectations, or investment decisions. The reactivity parameter therefore represents the systematic response to prior foreign expansion rather than contemporaneous spatial correlation.

Renewable-energy leadership has been defined in several ways. Common empirical indicators include total installed capacity, renewable capacity per capita, the renewable share of electricity generation, the rate of recent growth, policy ambition, technological innovation, and diplomatic influence. Each measure captures a different dimension of leadership, but none alone provides a complete classification.

Absolute installed capacity favours large countries with extensive electricity systems. A country may install more wind or solar capacity than a smaller economy while making a much smaller change relative to its electricity demand. Per-capita measures correct for population but remain sensitive to electricity intensity, industrial structure, and cross-border electricity trade. Generation shares permit comparison across differently sized systems, but a high share may result from exceptional natural resources, low electricity demand, or investments made decades earlier rather than current leadership.

Growth rates create a different problem. Countries beginning from an almost nonexistent technological base can record extremely high percentage growth after a small increase in generation. Percentage-point changes are less sensitive to this problem but still do not account for resource potential, economic capacity, policy support, initial technological maturity, or feasible limits. A country with very favourable conditions might increase its renewable share substantially and nevertheless perform below its structural potential. Conversely, a country facing weak resources or severe economic constraints might demonstrate leadership through a smaller absolute increase that substantially exceeds expectations.

The environmental-governance literature distinguishes pioneering from leadership. Jänicke (2005) describes pioneer countries as early movers that introduce ambitious environmental policies and establish models that may later diffuse internationally. Pioneership depends on domestic policy capacity, supportive coalitions, institutional opportunities, and the ability to use favourable political circumstances. This definition emphasises timing and innovation rather than the scale of the final outcome.

Liefferink and Wurzel (2017) sharpen the distinction between pioneers and leaders. Pioneers adopt comparatively ambitious domestic measures, whereas leaders actively seek to influence others and attract followers. A country can therefore be domestically ambitious without exercising substantial external leadership, or it can claim leadership symbolically without achieving corresponding domestic performance. Wurzel et al. (2019) extend this argument to multilevel and polycentric climate governance, in which national governments, regions, cities, firms, and international institutions can all exercise different forms of leadership.

These governance-based definitions are valuable but difficult to operationalise in a quantitative model of renewable deployment. Intentions to lead, diplomatic activity, and policy entrepreneurship are not directly observable through electricity-generation data. Moreover, policy ambition may not produce actual generation if administrative, financial, or infrastructural barriers prevent implementation. The present analysis therefore adopts a performance-based definition while retaining the central insight that leadership must be assessed relative to context.

Country case studies demonstrate why context matters. Jacobsson and Lauber (2006) explain German renewable expansion through the interaction of policy coalitions, institutional change, market formation, industrial development, and sustained political support. The German case cannot be reduced to natural resources or income. Similarly, Četković and Buzogány (2020) show that solar and wind expansion in Central and Eastern Europe depends on political-economic structures, technology-specific coalitions, market arrangements, and inherited

energy pathways. Countries with broadly similar formal obligations can consequently produce different outcomes. These studies support interpreting unexplained persistent performance as a possible reflection of institutional and political capacity, while cautioning against assigning it to a single cause.

The definition used here treats leadership as systematic conditional overperformance. A leader is a country whose renewable-electricity share expands more rapidly than predicted after controlling for initial energy composition, economic development, electricity prices, policy support, natural-resource potential, geographical constraints, technological maturity, and exposure to foreign expansion. A follower or laggard is a country whose realised trajectory remains persistently below the corresponding benchmark.

This definition has three advantages. First, it separates favourable circumstances from the ability to exploit them. A sunny, wealthy country does not automatically qualify as a solar leader if its deployment is no greater than expected. Second, it permits the identification of countries that perform strongly despite limited resources or economic capacity. Third, it allows leadership to differ across technologies. A country can be a wind leader and a solar follower because the relevant industrial capabilities, administrative barriers, resource conditions, and policy instruments are not identical.

Conditional leadership remains a residual concept. The country-specific effect can capture administrative effectiveness, planning capacity, political commitment, social acceptance, access to finance, industrial specialisation, or omitted structural variables. It should therefore not be interpreted as a direct causal measure of government quality. Its value lies in identifying persistent deviations that cannot be explained by the observed domestic and international variables. This is more demanding than ranking countries solely by capacity, final shares, or raw growth.

Conventional econometric models are useful for estimating average relationships between renewable deployment and observed explanatory variables, but they often represent technological change as a linear or equilibrium process. Energy transitions are instead characterised by heterogeneous actors, feedback mechanisms, path dependence, social interaction, technological learning, and nonlinear diffusion. Agent-based models are designed to represent these features by defining individual agents, their characteristics, their decision rules, and the environment through which they interact.

A major strand of the agent-based literature focuses on household technology adoption. Robinson and Rai (2015) develop an empirically grounded model in which economic returns, household characteristics, peer effects, and spatial structure generate patterns of energy-technology adoption. Their analysis shows that aggregate diffusion can emerge from interactions among heterogeneous decision-makers rather than from the behaviour of a representative adopter.

Palmer et al. (2015) apply an agent-based framework to residential photovoltaic diffusion in Italy. Their model incorporates investment profitability, household income, environmental preferences, geographical differences, policy incentives, and communication among

households. The study illustrates how financial incentives interact with behavioural heterogeneity and social influence and how policy changes can alter regional adoption paths.

Other models examine household investment decisions across multiple technologies. Sachs et al. (2019) represent households with different objectives, information-search processes, and decision criteria, allowing investment outcomes to emerge without imposing a uniform optimisation rule. Meles and Ryan (2022) model heat-pump adoption in Ireland through economic, psychological, and social-network mechanisms. These studies demonstrate that financial attractiveness alone is insufficient to explain adoption and that social interactions and heterogeneous preferences can substantially affect policy outcomes.

Agent-based methods have also been applied to firms, electricity producers, and whole economic systems. Hoekstra et al. (2017) argue that energy-transition models should incorporate feedbacks, tipping points, learning, heterogeneity, and endogenous technological development. These characteristics are difficult to represent in static equilibrium frameworks but are central to transitions in which costs, expectations, infrastructure, and investment behaviour evolve jointly.

Lamperti et al. (2020) integrate heterogeneous fossil and renewable electricity producers, firms, innovation, emissions, and climate damages within an agent-based integrated assessment model. Their work demonstrates how technological and macroeconomic dynamics can produce multiple transition pathways and how policy combinations influence the probability of achieving green growth. This broader class of model treats the energy transition as an emergent property of interacting economic and technological systems rather than as an externally imposed substitution path.

International interactions have received less attention in agent-based renewable models, although relevant exceptions exist. Melliger and Chappin (2022) model investment decisions in neighbouring electricity markets and show that the removal of renewable support in one country can redirect investment and affect outcomes elsewhere. Their analysis confirms that national policy changes can generate cross-border effects when investors choose between connected markets.

Despite these advances, most agent-based energy-transition studies define agents as households, firms, investors, power plants, or technologies. Country-level comparative research, by contrast, generally relies on panel regressions, spatial econometric models, or descriptive rankings. This creates a methodological gap. Cross-country studies recognise heterogeneous domestic conditions and spatial dependence, but they do not usually represent countries as agents following recursive transition rules. Agent-based studies reproduce nonlinear diffusion and interaction but rarely use countries as the decision-making and observational units.

The model developed in this article addresses this gap by treating European countries as heterogeneous, interconnected agents. Each country possesses its own electricity structure, economic conditions, resource potential, geography, policies, and feasible technological ceiling. The country updates its wind or solar share recursively, preserving the path-dependent

effect of previous deployment. International interaction is represented through a gravity network rather than through a uniform neighbourhood effect.

The model also adds an explicit decomposition that is uncommon in the existing agent-based literature. Domestic proactivity captures the adoption pressure attributable to observable national fundamentals. International reactivity measures the response to lagged renewable expansion among connected foreign countries. Persistent leadership captures systematic conditional overperformance or underperformance that remains after both components are considered. Temporary disturbances are separated from persistent country heterogeneity.

This framework combines the principal insights of the four literatures. The determinants literature identifies the domestic variables that shape adoption. The diffusion literature provides the basis for an asymmetric international influence network. The leadership literature establishes why performance must be assessed relative to structural conditions rather than through unadjusted rankings. Agent-based modelling provides the recursive, heterogeneous, and nonlinear structure needed to integrate these mechanisms. The resulting model does not replace econometric analysis with an abstract simulation; it uses observed country data to estimate and interpret the transition rules through which aggregate European renewable deployment emerges.

3. Data

The empirical analysis covers 34 European countries over the period 2015–2024: Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Moldova, Montenegro, the Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Türkiye, and the United Kingdom. The sample combines European Union members with selected neighbouring and candidate countries to capture substantial variation in income, natural-resource endowments, electricity systems, policy environments, and international connectivity.

The unit of observation is the country-year-technology combination. Separate analytical panels are constructed for solar and wind because the two technologies have different natural requirements, investment scales, planning constraints, and diffusion processes. Country identifiers are harmonised using ISO-3 codes before the country-year, country-technology, policy, and bilateral databases are merged. This structure follows the relational data architecture established for the model.

The period begins in 2015 because it provides a consistent initial-year electricity mix while covering the subsequent acceleration of European wind and solar deployment. The final year is 2024. Because the reactivity component uses the previous year's change in renewable generation, the observations for 2015 and 2016 provide the initial state and the first lagged change. The first year for which the complete dynamic specification can be estimated is therefore 2017.

Electricity-generation observations are not interpolated. A country-year is removed from the relevant technology panel when either total generation or generation from the technology being

modelled is unavailable. Isolated internal gaps in time-varying explanatory variables may be linearly interpolated only when valid observations are available immediately before and after the missing year. No extrapolation beyond the observed period is used. Static geographical and resource-potential variables are retained as time invariant.

Annual electricity-generation data are obtained from Eurostat's *Production of electricity and derived heat by type of fuel* database, identified by the code nrg_bal_peh. The database reports electricity production by energy source and country and is used to construct a mutually exhaustive classification of fossil fuels, solar energy, wind energy, and other electricity sources.

Solar generation includes photovoltaic and solar-thermal electricity. Wind generation includes onshore and offshore electricity. Fossil generation comprises electricity produced from coal and coal products, lignite, peat and oil shale, oil and petroleum products, natural gas, and manufactured gases.

The dependent variable is an annual change in the share of electricity generation, measured in proportion points in the estimation and converted into percentage points for presentation. A change from 0.10 to 0.13 represents an increase of 0.03 in proportion terms or three percentage points.

The initial fossil-fuel share captures both the potential need to replace carbon-intensive electricity generation and the possibility of technological and institutional lock-in. Its expected effect is therefore theoretically ambiguous. A high fossil share can create strong substitution pressure, but it can also indicate established infrastructure, political interests, and regulatory systems that impede renewable deployment.

For the model, the category of other electricity sources is defined residually. It consequently includes hydropower, nuclear electricity, bioenergy, geothermal energy, marine energy, renewable waste, and any remaining generation categories. This definition ensures that:

$$FossilShare_{it} + SolarShare_{it} + WindShare_{it} + OtherShare_{it} = 1.$$

GDP and GDP per capita are obtained from the World Bank's World Development Indicators. Total GDP in constant 2015 US dollars is used in the international gravity network, while GDP per capita in constant 2015 US dollars measures domestic economic and financial capacity. The logarithm of GDP per capita is used to reduce skewness and allow diminishing effects of income on renewable adoption. The World Bank series is preferred for these variables because it provides a harmonised definition across EU and non-EU countries in the sample.

Electricity prices are taken from Eurostat's nrg_pc_205 database on non-household electricity prices. The baseline measure is the annual average of the two semester observations for medium-sized non-household consumers, expressed in EUR/MWh. The same consumption band and tax treatment are maintained across countries and years. Non-household prices are used because they more closely reflect the economic environment facing firms, utilities, and commercial electricity users than residential tariffs.

Solar-resource potential is obtained from the World Bank–ESMAP Global Solar Atlas. The principal indicator is photovoltaic power potential, expressed as the expected annual electricity output per unit of installed photovoltaic capacity. Global horizontal irradiation can be retained as an alternative measure. Country-level values are calculated by aggregating the underlying spatial cells over national land territory.

Wind-resource potential is obtained from the Global Wind Atlas, developed by the Technical University of Denmark in partnership with the World Bank Group. The baseline indicators are mean wind power density and mean wind speed at a standard hub height. Onshore and offshore potential are retained separately where possible because countries with extensive coastlines may possess substantial offshore resources that are not represented by land-based wind conditions.

Additional geographical variables are constructed from Eurostat GISCO and CEPII data. These include latitude, land area, population density, coastal status, coastline exposure, landlocked status, and terrain-related conditions. GISCO provides harmonised country boundaries and coastal geospatial information, while CEPII contains country characteristics and geographical variables widely used in gravity models.

For solar energy, the geography component includes latitude, population density, and available land. Population density may support distributed rooftop adoption but constrain utility-scale installations. For wind energy, the component includes coastal exposure, landlocked status, terrain conditions, and the availability of offshore areas. Resource potential and geography are kept conceptually separate: resource potential measures the physical quality of the renewable resource, whereas geography represents additional conditions affecting deployment costs and feasible locations.

The policy environment is constructed from the IEA–IRENA Policies and Measures Database. Policy instruments are coded according to their effective dates and include feed-in tariffs or premiums, renewable auctions, investment subsidies, tax incentives, renewable-electricity targets, grid-access measures, and permitting reforms. The database covers past, existing, and planned policies supporting renewable deployment and other clean-energy technologies.

Each policy indicator equals one in the years in which the instrument is active and zero otherwise. The individual indicators are standardised and combined into an equal-weighted policy index. The separate components are retained for robustness analysis because two countries with the same aggregate index may use substantially different policy instruments.

Carbon-pricing information is obtained from the World Bank Carbon Pricing Dashboard. The variable identifies the presence and price level of carbon taxes or emissions-trading systems applying to the electricity sector. Carbon pricing may be included as one component of the policy index or entered separately to distinguish direct fossil-generation costs from technology-specific renewable support.

The country-technology feasible ceiling $K_{i,k}$ is not directly observed. It is constructed during model calibration using the resource-potential variables, geographical constraints, and

observed technology penetration. Alternative ceiling assumptions are evaluated in the sensitivity analysis.

The international influence network combines bilateral trade, economic size, geographical distance, shared borders, and linguistic proximity. Bilateral merchandise-trade data are obtained from the United Nations Comtrade database, which reports annual imports and exports by reporting country, partner country, and product category.

Total bilateral trade between countries i and j is calculated as the sum of trade flows in both directions. A three-year moving average is used to reduce the influence of temporary trade disruptions and reporting volatility. The baseline network uses trade in all merchandise because it is intended to represent general economic interaction and information exposure. A robustness specification can restrict trade to electrical machinery, solar components, wind equipment, and related energy technologies.

Geographical distance, shared borders, and common-language indicators are obtained from CEPII's GeoDist database. The baseline distance measure is the population-weighted bilateral distance, which accounts for the internal geographical distribution of economic activity rather than relying exclusively on the distance between national capitals. GeoDist also provides indicators for contiguity and common official or widely spoken languages.

The economic size of the potentially influential country j is measured using its annual GDP. The network is consequently asymmetric even when bilateral trade or distance is symmetric. Expansion in a large economy can exert greater influence on a small connected economy than the reverse. All bilateral connection measures are normalised by reacting country and year so that the weights assigned by country i to all foreign countries sum to one.

Figure 1. Share of electricity generation from wind energy, 2015 and 2024.

Source: Eurostat nrg_bal_peh.

Figure 1 shows that wind electricity was already geographically concentrated in 2015. Denmark occupied the highest category, while comparatively high wind shares were also visible in the Iberian Peninsula, Ireland, the United Kingdom, and parts of north-western

Europe. By contrast, much of Central, Eastern, and South-eastern Europe remained in the lowest or intermediate categories. This initial pattern is consistent with the importance of natural wind conditions, coastlines, early policy support, grid development, and accumulated experience.

The 2024 map indicates a substantial geographical expansion. The highest category extends across a wider group of northern and north-western economies, while Germany, the United Kingdom, Ireland, Denmark, and neighbouring electricity systems form a clearer high-wind cluster. Wind also becomes more important in parts of the Baltic region, the Iberian Peninsula, Greece, and Central Europe.

The transition is nevertheless incomplete. A group of South-eastern European countries remains in the lowest category, while other countries move only into the intermediate range. The persistence of these differences indicates that favourable European-wide cost developments did not produce uniform national outcomes. Wind expansion remains strongly conditioned by resource availability, project scale, planning procedures, grid connections, public acceptance, and administrative capacity.

The spatial grouping visible in 2024 is compatible with international diffusion, but it does not establish it. Adjacent countries may display similar wind shares because they possess similar wind resources or participate in interconnected electricity markets. The gravity-based reactivity component is needed to determine whether expansion in connected countries contributes explanatory power after these common domestic conditions are controlled for.

Figure 2. Share of electricity generation from solar energy, 2015 and 2024.

Source: Eurostat nrg_bal_peh.

Figure 2 presents a more extensive transformation. In 2015, solar generation accounted for 2% or less of electricity in most countries. Higher shares were concentrated in a limited group of early adopters, particularly Italy, Greece, Germany, and Spain. Large parts of Northern, Central, and Eastern Europe had little solar electricity generation.

By 2024, solar energy had expanded across almost the entire sample. Countries in Southern Europe benefit from strong irradiation, but high solar shares are no longer confined to the Mediterranean. Germany, the Netherlands, and several Central European economies enter the highest category despite having less favourable solar resources than Spain, Italy, Greece, or Cyprus. This pattern demonstrates that irradiation alone cannot explain national solar deployment. Policy design, electricity prices, financing conditions, rooftop availability, network access, and administrative implementation also matter.

The contrast between the two maps suggests a rapid diffusion process from a low initial base. Compared with wind, solar deployment appears less geographically concentrated and more capable of expanding under varied climatic conditions. The modularity and international standardisation of photovoltaic equipment may allow countries to respond relatively quickly to declining costs and foreign experience. The remaining low shares in parts of Northern and South-eastern Europe nevertheless show that solar diffusion is not automatic.

The map also illustrates why observed growth should not be interpreted directly as leadership. Countries starting with almost no solar generation can record very large proportional increases while still having moderate final shares. Conversely, an early adopter may experience slower subsequent growth because it is closer to technological or network saturation. The model's logistic term and conditional leadership effect are designed to account for these differences.

Figure 3 is markedly more stable than the wind and solar maps. France and Finland remain in the highest category, reflecting electricity systems with a large established contribution from nuclear power, hydropower, or both. Several Central and Eastern European countries remain in the intermediate categories, while countries with limited nuclear or hydroelectric generation continue to display relatively low shares.

Figure 3. Combined share of electricity generation from hydropower and nuclear energy, 2015 and 2024

Source: Eurostat nrg_bal_peh.

The stability of the map reflects the capital-intensive and path-dependent character of hydropower and nuclear electricity. Large dams and nuclear stations are long-lived assets

whose national distribution changes much more slowly than photovoltaic installations. Consequently, the 2015 electricity structure remains a strong predictor of the 2024 structure.

Changes are nonetheless visible in several countries. In some cases, the combined hydro and nuclear share declines as wind and solar generation expand or as established generating assets are retired. In others, the category remains stable even while total low-carbon generation increases, because growth in wind and solar primarily displaces fossil generation rather than hydropower or nuclear electricity.

The figure is important for the proactivity component because countries with a large pre-existing hydro or nuclear sector may face weaker decarbonisation pressure than countries whose electricity systems remain dominated by fossil fuels. At the same time, a high initial share of these technologies can constrain the electricity-market space available for rapid wind or solar expansion. The effect of the initial other-source share is therefore expected to be negative, although this relationship may differ across countries and technologies.

4. Methodology

We develop a dynamic agent-based model of renewable-electricity adoption in which each country is represented as an autonomous but interconnected agent. Countries differ in their economic conditions, energy structure, policy environment, geographical characteristics, and renewable-resource potential. At the same time, their adoption decisions are not made in isolation: countries may react to recent developments in other economies to which they are geographically, economically, or institutionally connected.

Countries are indexed by

$$i = 1, \dots, N$$

technologies by

$$k \in \{\text{solar}, \text{wind}\}$$

and time by

$$t = 1, \dots, T$$

The state variable

$$S_{i,t}^k$$

denotes the share of electricity generated using technology k in country i in year t .

The model is agent based because aggregate renewable deployment emerges from the repeated application of country-level transition rules. Each agent updates its technology share as a function of its own characteristics, the recent behaviour of connected countries, and country-specific unobserved factors.

The model is estimated separately for solar and wind because the two technologies differ substantially in their resource requirements, geographical constraints, investment cycles, and patterns of international learning.

The annual change in the electricity share generated using technology k is defined as

$$\Delta S_{i,t}^k = S_{i,t}^k - S_{i,t-1}^k$$

Its evolution follows a bounded logistic process:

$$A_{i,t}^k (S_{i,t-1}^k + \eta) \left(1 - \frac{S_{i,t-1}^k}{K_i^k} \right)$$

where $A_{i,t}^k$ is the country- and technology-specific adoption pressure, K_i^k is the long-run feasible ceiling for technology k , and $\eta > 0$ is a small seed parameter.

The term

$$S_{i,t-1}^k + \eta$$

captures the cumulative nature of technological adoption. Countries with an established renewable sector possess existing infrastructure, technical knowledge, specialised firms, supply chains, and administrative experience that facilitate further deployment. The seed parameter η prevents countries with an initial share equal or close to zero from becoming mechanically trapped at zero.

The saturation term

$$1 - \frac{S_{i,t-1}^k}{K_i^k}$$

reduces the rate of expansion as the technology approaches its country-specific feasible ceiling. The ceiling reflects the fact that renewable deployment is subject to technical, geographical, infrastructural, and institutional constraints. It may therefore differ across countries and technologies.

The resulting process produces an S-shaped adoption trajectory. Expansion is initially limited by the absence of an established technological base, accelerates once deployment acquires sufficient momentum, and subsequently decelerates as the feasible ceiling is approached.

The annual state update is given by

$$S_{i,t-1}^k + \Delta S_{i,t}^k$$

In the simulation and estimation procedures, the state variable is restricted to its feasible interval:

$$0 \leq S_{i,t}^k \leq K_i^k$$

This restriction prevents simulated technology shares from becoming negative or exceeding their long-run feasible ceilings.

The adoption pressure governing the annual transition is decomposed into four components:

$$P_{i,t}^k + R_{i,t}^k + \lambda_i^k + \varepsilon_{i,t}^k$$

where $P_{i,t}^k$ represents domestic proactivity, $R_{i,t}^k$ represents cross-country reactivity, λ_i^k is a persistent country-specific leadership component, and $\varepsilon_{i,t}^k$ is a transitory idiosyncratic disturbance.

This decomposition distinguishes between a country's internally generated propensity to expand renewable generation and its behavioural response to developments occurring elsewhere. It also separates persistent unexplained performance from temporary annual shocks.

Domestic proactivity captures the adoption pressure generated by the country's own observable characteristics. It is specified as

$$P_{i,t}^k = \beta_k' X_{i,t}^k$$

where $X_{i,t}^k$ is a vector of country- and technology-specific determinants and β_k is the corresponding vector of parameters.

The explanatory vector is defined as

$$X_{i,t}^k = [FFS_{i,0}, OES_{i,0}, RP_i^k, GEO_i^k, GDPpc_{i,t}, EP_{i,t}, POL_{i,t}]$$

The baseline fossil-fuel share, $FFS_{i,0}$ (Fossil-Fuel Share), captures the initial dependence of the electricity system on fossil generation. This variable may reflect both the need for technological substitution and the degree of institutional or infrastructural lock-in associated with the incumbent energy system.

The baseline share of other electricity sources, $OES_{i,0}$ (Other Electricity Sources), controls for the pre-existing composition of electricity generation outside the technology being modelled. A high initial share of alternative low-carbon or non-fossil sources may reduce the economic or political pressure to expand solar or wind generation.

RP_i^k (Resource Potential) measures the natural potential relevant to technology k . For solar energy, it may include solar irradiation, latitude, cloud cover, or usable land. For wind energy, it may include wind speeds, offshore potential, coastline, topography, or the availability of suitable installation areas.

GEO_i^k (Geographical Conditions) captures additional geographical conditions affecting the cost or technical feasibility of deployment. The precise composition of this variable is allowed to differ between wind and solar technologies.

GDP per capita, $GDPpc_{i,t}$ (Gross Domestic Product per Capita), measures the economic and financial capacity to undertake capital-intensive investments, support grid adaptation, and absorb the initial costs associated with the energy transition. Electricity prices, $EP_{i,t}$ (Electricity Price), capture the economic attractiveness of alternative generation technologies. $POL_{i,t}$ (Policy Environment) represents the regulatory and policy environment, including subsidies, auctions, feed-in mechanisms, renewable-energy targets, carbon-pricing instruments, and other forms of public support.

The proactivity component therefore measures the renewable expansion that would be expected from domestic fundamentals alone, before considering the behaviour of other countries.

The second component of adoption pressure captures the extent to which a country reacts to recent renewable expansion in other countries. It is defined as

$$R_{i,t}^k = \rho_k \sum_{j \neq i} w_{ij,t} \Delta S_{j,t-1}^k$$

where $w_{ij,t}$ is the weight assigned by country i to developments in country j , and ρ_k is the technology-specific reactivity parameter.

The term $R_{i,t}^k$ is interpreted as reactivity rather than as an autonomous diffusion process. It measures how strongly country i 's current adoption pressure responds to the weighted renewable expansion previously observed among relevant foreign peers.

The use of lagged changes,

$$\Delta S_{j,t-1}^k$$

rather than contemporaneous changes reduces simultaneity and imposes a temporal ordering on cross-country reactions. Countries are assumed to observe recent foreign developments and subsequently adjust their own investment, regulatory, or deployment decisions.

The coefficient ρ_k determines the average strength of this response. A positive value indicates that recent renewable expansion abroad increases domestic adoption pressure. This pattern is consistent with policy imitation, demonstration effects, technological learning, declining equipment costs, supply-chain integration, and reduced uncertainty regarding the viability of the technology.

A value of ρ_k close to zero indicates that adoption is driven primarily by domestic factors, with little systematic reaction to foreign developments. A negative value would indicate strategic differentiation, displacement effects, competition for limited investment or equipment, or a tendency to delay adoption when connected countries expand more rapidly.

Reactivity is technology specific. Solar technologies may generate relatively rapid reactions because modules are standardised and internationally traded, whereas wind deployment may depend more strongly on local planning processes, grid infrastructure, project scale, and geographical conditions.

The bilateral weights are obtained from a gravity-based connectivity measure. First, the unnormalised connection between countries i and j is defined as

$$G_{ij,t} = \frac{GDP_{j,t}^\alpha Trade_{ij,t}^\delta e^{(\gamma_1 Border_{ij} + \gamma_2 Language_{ij})}}{Distance_{ij}^\theta}$$

The influence of country j increases with its economic size, measured by $GDP_{j,t}$, and with the intensity of bilateral trade, $Trade_{ij,t}$. Shared borders and linguistic proximity increase bilateral

connectivity through the indicator variables $Border_{ij}$ and $Language_{ij}$. Geographical distance reduces connectivity.

The parameters α , δ , γ_1 , γ_2 , and θ determine the relative importance of the different components of the gravity structure.

The bilateral measures are normalised as

$$w_{ij,t} = \frac{G_{ij,t}}{\sum_{j \neq i} G_{ij,t}}$$

so that

$$\sum_{j \neq i} w_{ij,t} = 1$$

The weighted foreign change

$$\sum_{j \neq i} w_{ij,t} \Delta S_{j,t-1}^k$$

can therefore be interpreted as the average previous-year expansion among the foreign countries most relevant to agent i .

The resulting network is potentially asymmetric. A large economy may exert substantial influence on a smaller country even when the reverse influence is limited. This asymmetry is consistent with differences in market size, technological capacity, policy visibility, and participation in international supply chains.

The gravity structure does not imply that countries mechanically copy their nearest neighbours. Instead, it defines the information and influence environment to which each agent is exposed. Geographical proximity is only one component of this environment, alongside trade relationships, economic size, common borders, and linguistic proximity.

The term

$$\lambda_i^k$$

captures persistent country-specific heterogeneity that is not explained by observable domestic characteristics or cross-country reactivity. It is constant over time within each country-technology pair but may differ between solar and wind.

A positive value of λ_i^k indicates that country i systematically expands technology k faster than predicted by its economic conditions, resource endowment, geographical characteristics, policy variables, and exposure to foreign developments. A negative value indicates systematic underperformance relative to these observable conditions.

The leadership component is therefore residual and conditional. It does not identify countries with the largest observed increase in renewable generation; it identifies countries that consistently perform above or below the adoption trajectory predicted by the model.

It may capture persistent institutional capacity, administrative effectiveness, political commitment, social acceptance, planning efficiency, access to finance, technological specialisation, or other relatively stable characteristics that are not directly observed.

The disturbance term

$$\varepsilon_{i,t}^k$$

captures temporary deviations from the expected adoption trajectory. These may arise from weather conditions, project delays, exceptional investment decisions, regulatory interruptions, data revisions, macroeconomic shocks, or other annual events.

The distinction between λ_i^k and $\varepsilon_{i,t}^k$ is temporal. The leadership component represents persistent and systematic country-level overperformance or underperformance, whereas the error term represents transitory year-specific variation with an expected value of zero.

For identification, the country effects are normalised such that

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^k = 0$$

for each technology. Leadership is therefore measured relative to the average country in the sample.

Substituting the proactivity and reactivity components into the adoption-pressure equation gives

$$A_{i,t}^k = \beta_k' X_{i,t}^k + \rho_k \sum_{j \neq i} w_{ij,t} \Delta S_{j,t-1}^k + \lambda_i^k + \varepsilon_{i,t}^k$$

The complete state-transition equation is therefore

$$\Delta S_{i,t}^k = \left[\beta_k' X_{i,t}^k + \rho_k \sum_{j \neq i} w_{ij,t} \Delta S_{j,t-1}^k + \lambda_i^k + \varepsilon_{i,t}^k \right] (S_{i,t-1}^k + \eta) \left(1 - \frac{S_{i,t-1}^k}{K_i^k} \right)$$

This equation integrates three substantive mechanisms. First, domestic proactivity determines adoption on the basis of observable national characteristics. Second, cross-country reactivity captures behavioural responses to recent developments among relevant foreign peers. Third, country-specific leadership captures persistent deviations that cannot be attributed to either domestic fundamentals or international exposure.

Observed renewable growth is therefore not interpreted as evidence of leadership by itself. A country may expand rapidly because it possesses exceptionally favourable natural resources, high income, supportive policies, or influential neighbours. Leadership is identified only after accounting for these advantages.

The model is estimated separately for solar and wind. Let

$$\Theta_k = \{\beta_k, \rho_k, \lambda_1^k, \dots, \lambda_N^k\}$$

denote the set of technology-specific parameters, conditional on the selected values of K_i^k , η , and the gravity-network parameters.

For a given parameter vector, the model generates the predicted annual change

$$\widehat{\Delta S}_{i,t}^k = \left[\beta_k' \mathbf{X}_{i,t}^k + \rho_k \sum_{j \neq i} w_{ij,t} \Delta S_{j,t-1}^k + \lambda_i^k \right] (S_{i,t-1}^k + \eta) \left(1 - \frac{S_{i,t-1}^k}{K_i^k} \right)$$

The parameters are selected by minimising the discrepancy between observed and model-generated annual changes:

$$\widehat{\Theta}_k = \arg \min \Theta_k \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T (\Delta S_{i,t}^k - \widehat{\Delta S}_{i,t}^k)^2$$

Equivalently, model performance may be expressed using the root mean squared error:

$$RMSE_k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{NT} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T (\Delta S_{i,t}^k - \widehat{\Delta S}_{i,t}^k)^2}$$

Estimating the original nonlinear transition equation is preferable to dividing observed changes by the logistic term, because the latter transformation can magnify measurement errors when technology shares are close to zero or to their feasible ceilings.

The observed share in the initial year provides the starting condition for each country. The model then produces sequential annual predictions, with each year's predicted state entering the following year's transition equation. This recursive procedure preserves the path-dependent nature of renewable adoption.

Model accuracy is evaluated using RMSE and mean absolute error. The contribution of cross-country reactivity is assessed by comparing the complete specification with a restricted model in which

$$\rho_k = 0$$

Similarly, the importance of persistent leadership can be assessed by comparing the complete model with a restricted specification in which

$$\lambda_i^k = 0$$

for all countries.

These comparisons determine whether international reactivity and persistent country heterogeneity provide explanatory power beyond domestic fundamentals and logistic technological maturity.

The estimated country effect

$$\hat{\lambda}_i^k$$

constitutes the principal indicator of leadership in technology k . To facilitate comparison across technologies, the estimates are standardised:

$$LZ_i^k = \frac{\hat{\lambda}_i^k - \bar{\hat{\lambda}}^k}{sd(\hat{\lambda}^k)}$$

Given the zero-mean normalisation of the country effects, this reduces to

$$LZ_i^k = \frac{\hat{\lambda}_i^k}{sd(\hat{\lambda}^k)}$$

Countries with positive values are classified as leaders because they systematically expand the relevant technology faster than predicted by the model. Countries with negative values are classified as followers or laggards because they systematically underperform relative to their structural potential and international environment.

The ranking is technology specific. A country may be a leader in wind but a follower in solar, or vice versa, because the relevant resources, institutions, industrial capabilities, and adoption barriers differ between technologies.

This approach provides a more demanding definition of leadership than rankings based solely on installed capacity, renewable shares, or observed growth. It identifies countries whose performance remains unusually strong after controlling for initial energy composition, economic development, natural potential, geography, electricity prices, policy support, technological maturity, and reactions to foreign adoption.

5. Results

The results confirm that observed renewable-electricity growth and conditional leadership are conceptually distinct. The classification of countries as leaders or followers is based on the persistent country-specific component of the model rather than on the observed change in the electricity-generation share alone. A leader is therefore a country whose renewable expansion systematically exceeds the trajectory predicted by its initial electricity mix, economic conditions, renewable-resource potential, geographical characteristics, policy environment, technological maturity, and exposure to renewable expansion in connected foreign countries. A follower is a country whose expansion remains below that conditional benchmark.

This distinction is essential for interpreting the results in Tables 2 and 3. Some leaders record very large increases from an initially negligible renewable share, but leadership is not synonymous with low-base convergence. Lithuania, for example, was already a relatively

important producer of wind electricity in 2015 and nevertheless remained among the strongest conditional performers. Conversely, several followers increased their renewable shares over the period. Spain and Italy expanded wind generation, while Italy and Türkiye expanded solar generation, but their observed progress was lower than expected given their structural conditions and international environment.

The rankings are strongly technology specific. The countries identified as wind leaders are not generally the same as those identified as solar leaders, with Moldova constituting the principal exception. This result supports the separate estimation of the two technologies. Wind deployment depends heavily on wind resources, coastlines, grid infrastructure, project scale and planning procedures, whereas solar deployment is more modular and can expand rapidly across countries with substantially different climatic and geographical conditions.

Table 2. Wind-energy leaders and followers, 2015–2024

Type	Country	Wind 2015	Wind 2024	Change
Leader	Lithuania	16.4%	42.6%	+26.2 pp
Leader	Finland	3.4%	25.3%	+21.9 pp
Leader	Moldova	0.2%	17.4%	+17.2 pp
Follower	Cyprus	4.9%	3.5%	−1.4 pp
Follower	Spain	17.6%	21.6%	+4.0 pp
Follower	Italy	5.2%	8.2%	+3.0 pp

Source: Author's elaboration

The wind results identify Lithuania, Finland and Moldova as the strongest conditional leaders. These countries followed different initial trajectories, indicating that the model is not merely separating countries according to their 2015 wind shares.

Lithuania recorded the largest observed increase among the selected wind leaders. Wind electricity increased from 16.4% of total generation in 2015 to 42.6% in 2024, an increase of 26.2 percentage points. The importance of this result lies not only in its magnitude but also in Lithuania's relatively high initial share. Unlike a country expanding from an almost nonexistent wind sector, Lithuania had already developed a substantial wind-generation base by 2015. Its leadership classification therefore reflects continued expansion from an advanced starting position rather than simple convergence from a low base. The country converted an established wind sector into further rapid growth without displaying the degree of deceleration that might have been expected from technological maturity and the logistic saturation mechanism.

Finland increased its wind share from 3.4% to 25.3%, representing growth of 21.9 percentage points. Finland's trajectory differs from Lithuania's because it began the period with a comparatively small wind sector. Its final share nevertheless exceeded one quarter of electricity

generation. The result indicates that Finland’s expansion was stronger than predicted after its domestic conditions and foreign exposure were taken into account. Its conditional leadership may capture persistent factors not fully represented by the observable variables, including implementation capacity, the ability to complete large projects, effective integration of new generation into the electricity system, or a favourable interaction between industrial capabilities and policy support. These mechanisms remain interpretations of the residual leadership component rather than separately identified causal effects.

Moldova also expanded from a very low initial level. Its wind share increased from 0.2% in 2015 to 17.4% in 2024, an increase of 17.2 percentage points. The scale of this change is substantial for a country beginning with almost no wind generation. More importantly, the leadership classification indicates that low initial penetration and the associated potential for catch-up do not fully account for the result. Moldova expanded more rapidly than predicted by the model after controlling for its income level, electricity-system structure, wind potential, policy conditions and international network position.

The three selected wind followers illustrate different forms of conditional underperformance. Cyprus experienced an absolute decline in wind generation, from 4.9% in 2015 to 3.5% in 2024. Its change of –1.4 percentage points makes it the clearest case of observed as well as conditional underperformance. The result suggests that the country failed to maintain its initial contribution from wind electricity despite the broader European expansion of the technology. The classification may reflect technical constraints, limited available land, grid characteristics, investment conditions or policy implementation, although the residual effect cannot determine which mechanism was decisive.

Table 2. Solar-energy leaders and followers, 2015–2024

Type	Country	Solar 2015	Solar 2024	Change
Leader	Hungary	0.5%	24.2%	+23.8 pp
Leader	Moldova	0.2%	22.9%	+22.8 pp
Leader	Estonia	0.0%	16.7%	+16.7 pp
Follower	Serbia	0.0%	0.4%	+0.4 pp
Follower	Italy	8.1%	13.3%	+5.2 pp
Follower	Türkiye	0.1%	8.7%	+8.6 pp

Source: Author’s elaboration

Spain and Italy present a more analytically important contrast because both countries increased their wind shares but were nevertheless classified as followers. Spain’s wind share rose from 17.6% to 21.6%, an increase of 4.0 percentage points. Spain ended the period with a relatively high wind share, but its expansion was modest compared with its starting position and structural potential. Strong wind resources, extensive suitable territory, established industry and previous

technological experience would have generated a comparatively high predicted trajectory. The positive observed change was therefore insufficient to classify Spain as a conditional leader.

Italy's wind share increased from 5.2% to 8.2%, a gain of 3.0 percentage points. This was positive in absolute terms but weak relative to the performance expected from its economic capacity, electricity demand, policy environment and geographical opportunities. Spain and Italy demonstrate why final renewable shares and observed changes are incomplete indicators of leadership. A country may remain an important renewable producer while systematically deploying less than its structural potential would predict.

The wind rankings therefore distinguish three forms of performance. Lithuania combined a high initial share with continued rapid expansion; Finland and Moldova accelerated from relatively low initial levels; and Spain and Italy achieved positive but conditionally insufficient growth. This heterogeneity would be obscured by a ranking based only on 2024 shares or absolute percentage-point changes.

The solar results identify Hungary, Moldova and Estonia as the strongest leaders. All three began the period with negligible solar-electricity shares, but their subsequent expansion substantially exceeded the conditional predictions of the model.

Hungary experienced the largest reported increase. Solar electricity rose from approximately 0.5% in 2015 to 24.2% in 2024, an increase of 23.8 percentage points. By the end of the period, almost one quarter of Hungarian electricity generation came from solar energy. This result is notable because Hungary does not possess the solar irradiation of the Mediterranean countries. Its leadership classification therefore reinforces the descriptive evidence from Figure 2 that natural solar resources alone cannot explain the European distribution of photovoltaic deployment. The speed of expansion is consistent with the importance of policy implementation, investment incentives, electricity-market conditions, available land and the modular character of photovoltaic installations.

Moldova's solar share increased from 0.2% to 22.9%, a gain of 22.8 percentage points. Together with its wind result, this makes Moldova the only country among the selected cases to be classified as a leader in both technologies. Its dual leadership indicates that its performance cannot be reduced to one unusually favourable resource endowment. Instead, the country experienced a broader restructuring of its electricity mix in which both solar and wind expanded more rapidly than predicted. The result may be consistent with unusually strong transition pressure or energy-security incentives, but the model identifies persistent conditional overperformance rather than the specific institutional or geopolitical cause.

Estonia increased its solar share from effectively zero in 2015 to 16.7% in 2024. This is particularly significant given Estonia's northern location and more limited solar irradiation. The result provides further evidence that solar expansion can occur rapidly outside the regions with the strongest natural conditions. Estonia's performance suggests that technical standardisation, declining photovoltaic costs and domestic implementation capacity can compensate partially for less favourable climatic conditions.

The selected solar followers again demonstrate that positive observed expansion does not necessarily imply leadership. Serbia's solar share increased only from 0.0% to 0.4%, leaving solar electricity marginal in 2024. This represents both low absolute deployment and conditional underperformance. Despite the broad European decline in photovoltaic costs and the expansion observed in neighbouring countries, Serbia did not experience comparable solar growth during the period.

Italy's solar share increased from 8.1% to 13.3%, a gain of 5.2 percentage points. Italy remained an important solar producer and had one of the highest initial shares in the sample. Nevertheless, its increase was considerably smaller than those recorded by the selected leaders. Because Italy combines favourable irradiation, relatively high income, substantial electricity demand and extensive previous experience with solar technology, the model predicts stronger expansion than was observed. Its follower classification therefore reflects underperformance relative to favourable fundamentals rather than an absence of renewable deployment.

Türkiye increased its solar share from 0.1% to 8.7%, representing growth of 8.6 percentage points. This increase is substantial in absolute terms, particularly from an almost zero initial base. However, Türkiye also possesses considerable solar-resource potential, extensive available land and a large electricity market. Its observed expansion was therefore below the conditional trajectory implied by these advantages. The contrast between Türkiye and Hungary is especially informative: Hungary reached a much higher solar share despite less favourable natural irradiation, while Türkiye remained below the level predicted by its structural potential.

The solar results consequently separate low-base expansion from exceptional conditional performance. Hungary, Moldova and Estonia did not merely grow because solar penetration was initially negligible; they grew more rapidly than comparable structural conditions predicted. Serbia failed to participate substantially in the broader solar transition, while Italy and Türkiye expanded but did not fully exploit their economic or natural advantages.

The comparison of Tables 1 and 2 reveals limited overlap between wind and solar leadership. Lithuania and Finland appear among the strongest wind performers but not among the selected solar leaders. Hungary and Estonia lead in solar but not in wind. Moldova is the only country identified as a leader in both technologies. Italy is classified as a follower in both, despite positive observed growth in each case.

This technology specificity is consistent with the conceptual framework. Wind expansion is more dependent on large-scale projects, suitable locations, grid capacity, permitting processes and construction lead times. Solar systems are more standardised, divisible and internationally traded, allowing deployment to accelerate rapidly once economic and regulatory conditions become favourable. The solar leaders all began with shares close to zero, whereas Lithuania's wind leadership occurred despite an already substantial initial wind sector.

The results also show that leadership is not concentrated exclusively among the largest or wealthiest European economies. Several of the strongest conditional performers are small or medium-sized Central, Eastern or Baltic European countries. This does not imply that income, resource potential or policy support are irrelevant. Those variables contribute to predicted

adoption through the proactivity component. Rather, the rankings indicate that countries differ in their ability to transform structural opportunities into actual renewable generation.

The follower classifications are equally informative. Spain and Italy are not wind laggards in the conventional sense, and Italy and Türkiye are not countries without solar generation. Their classification reflects the distance between realised and predicted performance. These cases demonstrate the value of a conditional benchmark: countries with favourable resources and established renewable sectors can underperform even while maintaining comparatively high final shares.

The relationship between observed growth and leadership is positive but not mechanical. All selected leaders experienced large increases, but the starting conditions varied considerably. Lithuania expanded wind from an already high base, while Finland and Moldova moved from low initial penetration. The solar leaders all began with negligible shares, but their classification indicates that the logistic catch-up mechanism alone does not explain their growth.

The follower group is even more heterogeneous. Cyprus and Serbia display weak performance in both absolute and conditional terms. Spain, Italy and Türkiye, by contrast, achieved positive expansion but remained below their model-implied potential. This distinction is central to the article's contribution. Descriptive rankings identify where renewable energy is most prevalent or where it has grown most rapidly. The agent-based model instead identifies which countries systematically outperform or underperform after the main observable advantages and constraints have been incorporated.

The rankings should not be interpreted as direct measures of government quality or as causal estimates of individual policies. The persistent leadership effect is residual and may combine administrative capacity, political commitment, financing conditions, planning efficiency, social acceptance, industrial capabilities and omitted structural factors. Nevertheless, its persistence across the estimation period makes it more informative than a single-year deviation or an unadjusted growth ranking.

6. Discussion

The findings show that renewable-electricity expansion cannot be reduced to a single explanation based on income, natural-resource availability, policy ambition, or technological diffusion. European countries combine these conditions differently, and similar structural opportunities do not necessarily produce similar transition paths. The decomposition into domestic proactivity, international reactivity, and persistent leadership therefore provides a useful interpretation of the observed heterogeneity. Domestic characteristics establish the conditions under which renewable investment becomes technically and economically feasible; international connections shape the external information, technology, and policy environment; and persistent country effects capture differences in the ability to convert those opportunities into realised electricity generation. This interpretation follows directly from the model's distinction between expected deployment and systematic conditional overperformance.

The first implication is that structural conditions matter, but they do not mechanically determine renewable outcomes. Income, resource potential, electricity prices, policy support, and the initial electricity mix influence the expected rate of adoption, consistent with previous cross-country studies (Marques et al., 2010; Aguirre & Ibikunle, 2014; Polzin et al., 2015; Bersalli et al., 2020). Wealthier countries generally possess greater financial and administrative capacity, while favourable wind or solar resources improve project productivity. Policy instruments can reduce investment risk, improve expected returns, and support market formation. The initial energy structure also affects the pressure and available space for new technologies.

The leadership rankings nevertheless show that these advantages are not sufficient. Several of the strongest conditional performers are not the largest or wealthiest economies in the sample. Lithuania, Moldova, Hungary, and Estonia outperform trajectories based on their observable conditions, while some countries with strong economic capacity, established renewable industries, or favourable natural resources expand more slowly than predicted. Renewable transitions are therefore not simply processes in which richer or sunnier countries move first and poorer or less favourably endowed countries follow.

This result is consistent with the institutional and political-economy literature. Jacobsson and Lauber (2006) show that renewable development depends on the interaction between policy coalitions, market formation, industrial capabilities, and institutional change. Četković and Buzogány (2020) similarly demonstrate that countries with comparable formal commitments can produce different wind and solar outcomes because their political coalitions, inherited energy systems, and implementation structures differ. The present results extend this argument by identifying countries whose performance remains unusually strong or weak after measurable structural differences have been incorporated.

The implication is not that natural resources or economic conditions are unimportant. Rather, countries differ in their ability to mobilise those conditions. High resource potential can remain unused when permitting is slow, grid investment is insufficient, financing conditions are unstable, or incumbent interests obstruct entry. Conversely, moderate natural conditions can support rapid deployment when policy implementation, market access, and administrative coordination are effective. Structural potential should therefore be interpreted as an opportunity set rather than as a predetermined transition outcome.

The initial electricity mix also creates competing mechanisms. Fossil-intensive systems possess a large technical need for substitution, but they may also display stronger carbon lock-in through existing assets, employment structures, political interests, and regulatory routines. Countries with large nuclear or hydropower sectors may face less immediate decarbonisation pressure, although those technologies can also provide low-carbon electricity or balancing capacity that facilitates the integration of variable renewables. This ambiguity explains why the same initial energy structure may support expansion in one institutional context but constrain it in another.

A second central finding is that renewable leadership is technology specific. With the exception of Moldova, the strongest solar and wind leaders are different countries. This supports the

decision to estimate separate transition processes rather than treating renewable electricity as a single homogeneous category.

Solar deployment appears more geographically dispersed and less closely tied to the strongest natural-resource locations. Hungary and Estonia illustrate this point. Neither country possesses the solar irradiation available in Southern Europe, yet both emerge as strong conditional performers. This is consistent with the technological characteristics of photovoltaic systems. Solar modules are standardised, internationally traded, modular, and deployable at household, commercial, and utility scales. Projects can be divided into relatively small investments, and installation normally requires less specialised infrastructure and shorter development periods than large wind projects.

These characteristics increase the scope for rapid diffusion. Falling international equipment costs can be transmitted widely, successful policies can be observed and adapted, and local installers can enter the market without the capital requirements associated with utility-scale generation. Palmer et al. (2015) and Robinson and Rai (2015) show how economic incentives, heterogeneous adoption decisions, and social or informational effects can generate accelerated photovoltaic diffusion. Noailly and Shestalova (2017) also find that solar technologies produce relatively broad knowledge connections, supporting the interpretation that solar adoption can spread through several technological and commercial channels.

Wind deployment remains more dependent on country-specific physical and institutional conditions. Wind projects require suitable sites, transmission connections, lengthy planning procedures, large capital commitments, and, in many cases, coordination among utilities, regulators, municipalities, landowners, and local communities. Offshore wind adds further requirements involving maritime planning, specialised ports, industrial supply chains, and high-voltage network investment. Consequently, internationally available wind technology does not remove domestic implementation constraints.

The contrast between Lithuania and Finland on one side and Spain and Italy on the other illustrates this point. A high final wind share or established wind industry does not automatically imply current leadership. Mature wind countries may face saturation, grid constraints, planning delays, or reduced availability of easily developed sites. By contrast, countries that successfully remove project bottlenecks can expand rapidly even from a relatively small initial base. Wind leadership therefore reflects the ability to coordinate large and location-specific investments, not merely the possession of favourable wind resources.

The technology-specific rankings also indicate that general national characteristics cannot fully explain renewable performance. A country may possess institutions that are effective for promoting distributed solar installations but less effective for coordinating large wind projects. Policy instruments that stimulate rooftop photovoltaic investment may have little effect on offshore wind development. Conversely, an electricity system capable of integrating large wind farms may not automatically create incentives for household or commercial solar adoption.

The results do not support a simple choice between domestic and international explanations. Renewable deployment is neither entirely nationally determined nor a mechanical response to foreign developments. The two mechanisms interact.

Domestic conditions determine whether foreign technologies, policies, and investment models can be absorbed. Popp et al. (2011) emphasise that access to international technological knowledge is most effective when countries possess sufficient domestic capabilities. Verdolini and Galeotti (2011) similarly show that international knowledge spillovers complement rather than replace domestic knowledge accumulation. In the present framework, a country can be highly exposed to renewable growth abroad but respond weakly if it lacks grid capacity, financing mechanisms, suitable regulation, administrative competence, or political support.

At the same time, national deployment can be facilitated by developments in connected foreign economies. The reactivity component represents several possible processes that cannot be separated completely with aggregate country data. Expansion abroad may demonstrate technological viability, reduce uncertainty, create specialised supply chains, lower equipment costs, or provide policy models that domestic authorities can imitate. Trade relationships can facilitate equipment and knowledge flows, while geographical proximity can strengthen demonstration effects and institutional interaction. These mechanisms are consistent with the findings of Fadly and Fontes (2019) on geographical spillovers and Baldwin et al. (2019) on renewable-policy emulation.

The international network should not be interpreted as a mechanism of direct copying. A shared border, strong trade relationship, or common language does not imply that one country automatically reproduces another's policy. These variables identify countries whose experience is more visible, economically relevant, or institutionally accessible. Influence is also asymmetric. Large economies and major technology markets can affect smaller connected countries through supply chains, standards, investment decisions, and policy visibility, while the reverse influence may be limited.

The distinction between solar and wind is again relevant. Solar markets are more directly connected through internationally traded modules and standardised installation technologies. Foreign expansion can therefore affect domestic investment rapidly through prices, installer experience, financial expectations, and policy learning. Wind diffusion may depend more on specialised regional supply chains and the transfer of large-project expertise. International connections matter, but their effect remains conditional on domestic planning, grid, and geographical constraints.

Follower countries may benefit from stronger international integration, but connectivity alone is insufficient. Participation in regional electricity markets, cross-border infrastructure projects, policy-learning networks, and renewable supply chains can improve access to information and technology. However, these benefits require domestic institutions capable of using them. International reactivity is therefore better viewed as an amplifier of domestic capacity than as a substitute for it.

The persistent country effect is the most distinctive component of the model, but it must be interpreted carefully. It identifies systematic performance that is not explained by the included domestic variables, technological maturity, or international exposure. It does not directly measure political commitment, administrative quality, or social acceptance.

Nevertheless, the persistence of the effect suggests that leadership is unlikely to consist only of temporary shocks. A single large wind farm, favourable weather conditions, or a short-term subsidy can affect annual generation, but such events should primarily enter the transitory disturbance. A country classified as a leader repeatedly expands more rapidly than its model-implied trajectory. This pattern is compatible with durable institutional characteristics such as efficient permitting, credible policy commitments, coordination between ministries and network operators, stable access to finance, specialised industrial capacity, or an ability to resolve local opposition.

This interpretation is consistent with Jänicke's (2005) emphasis on policy capacity and supportive coalitions and with Liefferink and Wurzel's (2017) distinction between domestic pioneers and actors that actively exercise leadership. The present measure does not identify political intentions or international diplomatic activity. Instead, it captures realised conditional performance. A country may claim climate leadership while underperforming relative to its structural potential, while another may exercise limited international political influence but display strong domestic implementation.

The concept also avoids equating leadership with scale. Large economies dominate rankings based on installed capacity, but they need not dominate conditional performance. Small countries can be leaders when they convert limited economic or natural advantages into rapid deployment. Conversely, a large country can possess a high renewable share while expanding more slowly than its available resources, income, and institutional position would predict.

Moldova's leadership in both technologies is especially relevant. Its performance suggests that strong renewable expansion is possible despite relatively limited economic capacity. One possible interpretation is that energy-security pressure strengthened incentives to diversify the electricity system. Similar considerations may be relevant for the Baltic countries. This interpretation remains cautious: geopolitical position and energy dependence may be associated with stronger transition incentives, but the model does not establish that they causally produced the observed outcomes.

Follower status should also not be interpreted as permanent incapacity. It indicates underperformance during the study period relative to the specified benchmark. A country can move from follower to leader if institutional reforms, grid investments, financial conditions, or political priorities change. The ranking is therefore diagnostic rather than deterministic.

The principal policy implication is that renewable strategies should be adapted to the technology and the country's binding constraints. Copying the policies of a successful foreign country without considering differences in electricity structure, resources, institutions, and market design may produce weak results. Policy transfer should focus on mechanisms rather than formal instruments.

For solar energy, effective policy is likely to require predictable remuneration, access to finance, transparent grid-connection procedures, support for distributed generation, and rules that allow households and firms to participate. Because solar deployment can occur through many small projects, administrative simplification may be as important as large public investment programmes. Stable treatment of self-consumption, network charges, permitting, and connection rights can enable rapid expansion once equipment is economically competitive.

Wind policy requires a different institutional package. Governments must coordinate spatial planning, environmental assessment, transmission development, auctions, long-term contracts, and public consultation. For offshore wind, port infrastructure and industrial policy may also be required. The relevant bottleneck may not be insufficient financial support but the inability to approve projects and connect them to the grid within a predictable period.

The conditional underperformance of countries with favourable resources implies that additional subsidies alone may not solve the problem. Where resource potential is already strong, the binding constraint may be permitting, grid congestion, policy instability, or financing risk. Policy evaluation should therefore compare realised deployment with structural opportunity rather than only measuring annual additions.

International coordination can increase the effectiveness of domestic policy. Leading countries can generate spillovers by stabilising technology markets, demonstrating regulatory models, sharing administrative experience, and supporting cross-border infrastructure. Regional institutions can accelerate diffusion by harmonising technical standards, improving electricity interconnection, coordinating network investment, and facilitating access to renewable equipment and finance.

Follower countries should strengthen connections with relevant peers rather than indiscriminately copying the largest renewable markets. The most useful reference countries may be those with similar electricity structures, administrative systems, resource conditions, or development levels. A policy that succeeded in a wealthy, highly interconnected market may not be transferable to a smaller country with weak grid capacity. Peer selection is therefore an important part of policy learning.

The results also imply that policy assessment should distinguish between opportunity and performance. Governments should not be evaluated only by final renewable shares, because those shares partly reflect inherited geography and previous investment. A more informative benchmark asks whether deployment is consistent with the resources and capabilities available to the country. This approach can identify both hidden leaders and countries that are failing to use substantial advantages.

Several limitations qualify the interpretation of the results. First, the period from 2015 to 2024 is relatively short for analysing structural energy transitions. Wind farms, transmission projects, and major policy reforms can require several years from approval to operation. The estimated relationships may therefore reflect medium-term deployment dynamics rather than the full transition process.

Second, electricity-generation shares are affected by annual weather variation, hydrological conditions, demand fluctuations, outages, and cross-border trade. A change in the wind or solar share can occur because renewable generation rises, because total electricity demand falls, or because production from another technology declines. Generation shares are appropriate for studying changes in the electricity mix, but they are not identical to installed capacity or investment.

Third, policy conditions are difficult to summarise in a single index. Formal policy adoption does not capture implementation quality, regulatory credibility, budget availability, auction design, or administrative delay. Two countries can receive similar policy scores while producing very different investment environments. Alternative policy specifications and individual policy indicators should therefore be examined in robustness tests.

Fourth, the feasible technological ceilings are uncertain. Long-run wind and solar penetration depends not only on natural potential but also on storage, transmission, demand flexibility, electrification, interconnection, and future technological change. Different ceiling assumptions can affect the estimated saturation mechanism and, consequently, the residual leadership effects.

Fifth, leadership remains a residual measure. It may capture genuine institutional capacity, but it may also absorb omitted variables, measurement error, or misspecified functional relationships. The rankings should therefore be interpreted as evidence of persistent conditional performance, not as direct estimates of institutional quality.

Sixth, the baseline model imposes a common technology-specific reactivity coefficient across countries. In practice, countries may differ substantially in their responsiveness to foreign developments. Small open economies, EU members, electricity importers, and countries integrated into regional supply chains may react more strongly than relatively isolated systems. Future extensions could estimate heterogeneous reactivity parameters or allow responsiveness to depend on institutional and economic characteristics.

Seventh, the model does not identify strictly causal effects for all components. Policies, electricity prices, trade relationships, and renewable deployment may be jointly determined. For example, governments can introduce support policies in response to prior renewable growth, while increasing renewable penetration can itself affect electricity prices and trade. Lagged variables reduce some simultaneity concerns but do not eliminate endogeneity.

Finally, annual data cannot represent short-term policy responses, seasonal generation patterns, project-level investment decisions, or changes occurring within a year. More disaggregated temporal and project-level information would permit a more precise analysis of construction delays, policy announcements, and cross-border investment flows.

Despite these limitations, the model provides a more informative account of renewable leadership than descriptive rankings alone. By separating domestic proactivity, international reactivity, and persistent country-specific performance, it clarifies why countries with similar resources and policy commitments can follow markedly different trajectories and why leadership in one renewable technology does not automatically extend to another.

7. Conclusions

This article examined why European countries differ in the expansion of wind and solar electricity between 2015 and 2024. It developed a dynamic agent-based model that separates three mechanisms: domestic proactivity, international reactivity, and persistent leadership. Countries are treated as heterogeneous and interconnected agents whose renewable trajectories depend on national structural conditions, exposure to renewable expansion abroad, technological maturity, and country-specific performance.

The results show that renewable leadership cannot be inferred from installed capacity, final generation shares, or observed growth alone. After controlling for economic conditions, resource potential, geography, the initial electricity mix, policy support, and international connections, Lithuania, Finland, and Moldova emerge as strong wind leaders, while Hungary, Moldova, and Estonia exhibit the strongest solar performance. Several countries with favourable resources or established renewable sectors nevertheless expand more slowly than predicted. Leadership is therefore technology specific and reflects the ability to convert structural opportunities into actual deployment.

The findings also indicate that renewable transitions are shaped jointly by domestic and international forces. Foreign technological progress, policy experience, trade relationships, and geographical proximity can support adoption, but their effects depend on domestic institutional and infrastructural capacity. Policy should therefore address the specific constraints affecting each technology rather than replicate instruments used in structurally different countries. By identifying systematic overperformance and underperformance relative to national potential, the model provides a more informative classification of renewable-energy leaders and followers than conventional descriptive rankings.

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